

THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPING MEDIAMADANISM IN FUTURE ENGINEER-EDUCATORS.

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Annotation

This article will talk about one of the concepts that have recently entered our lives, Media culture, as well as its role in the activities of engineers and educators.

Keywords

Media, competency, Culture, media, civilization, civil society, mediasavol, method.

Today, the role of the media in the life of society in our country is growing toboro. Almost all aspects of human life cannot be imagined without media. The skills of working, disseminating, disposing and transmitting information determine the level of competence and culture of a modern person. The granting of the status of the fourth power to the media, as well as the direct media coverage of political processes, tastes the incomparable role of the individual and the state, society in ensuring harmony. The scientific methodological foundations of the use of multimedia even in the educational process and its effective methods have been proven to this day through numerous pedagogical scientific studies, practical experimental test work.

In cultural studies, mediamadanism refers to the modern term that emerged and formed in the 20th century under the influence of the media. The term refers to the general and intellectual influence that media (primarily television, but also press, radio, and film) imposes not only on public opinion, but also on tastes and values.

Media culture is a term that combines two words, "media" and "culture". Media refers to various means of communication, such as television, radio, newspapers and the internet. It plays a decisive role in disseminating information, forming public opinion and influencing the dynamics of society. Culture is an Arabic term that translates as "civilization" or "civil society". It includes values, principles and practices that promote an inclusive and democratic society.

"Culture" emphasizes the active participation of citizens, respect for human rights, equality, justice and community solidarity.

Mediamadanism can be understood as a crossroads of media and civil society. It refers to the role of the media in the development of an active civil society by providing accurate information, encouraging public discussion and dialogue, encouraging citizen participation in decision-making processes, and holding those in power accountable. In essence, Media culture seeks to ensure that the media act as guardian of democracy by providing impartial information, promoting open discussion on social issues, empowering marginal voices, and ensuring transparency in governance. He acknowledges the power of the media in shaping public opinion and is an advocate of responsible journalism supporting democratic values.

Engineering educators will be associated with developing mediamadanism, explaining important aspects of mediamadanism, participating in the learning and teaching processes of mediamadanism, composing lectures for students and teachers, teaching the use of advanced and effective media tools.

The content of the development of mediamadanism can consist of the following main elements:

1. The essence of mediamadanism: in this part, engineer-educators must provide technical support to students to teach basic concepts and principles of mediamadanism, analyze mediacanals, learn to compose targeted and meaningful media messages.

2. Mediasavollar: in this part, engineer-educators must provide students with question-analysis work in mediamadaniyot. Through questions, students can analyse media materials, complete assignments about suspicious messages about exposure, and organize group work to strengthen knowledge.

3. Teaching methods and resources: engineer-educators must teach students learning methods in the process of developing mediamadanism. These methods may include interactive textbooks, video lessons, online lectures, media materials, etc.

4. Mediacanal organization: engineer-educators should teach students how to organize mediacanals to express their opinions and help them learn to communicate through the media. In the process, students are involved in blogging, video making, podcasting, etc.

5. Critical thinking and impressiveness: an important element in the development of Mediamadanism is the study of critical thinking in relation to impressiveness. Students learn to analyze the message and information displayed

in the media, assess whether they are intended for authenticity, and deal with satisfying messages.

6. Using Media tools: engineer educators should help students learn how to teach using Advanced media tools as well as what target topics they find in the media and search for additional information for them. In this process, students use media tools such as the internet, TV channels, radio, etc.

Engineers-educators need to study the content of the development of their mediamadanism and acquire the necessary knowledge and skills for its implementation. In this, it is important to develop the skills of students to effectively use the media, gain skills and experience, assess effectiveness and deal with suspicious messages. Engineers-educators attached great importance to the development of mediamadanism. Media culture includes the study of MediaTek work, the use of ICT, information streaming and other services. In order to develop mediamadanism, engineering educators must pay attention to the following content:

-The use of information and Communication Technologies: Engineering educators explain to students how information is sought, found and used in media. Through these technologies, students learn how to apply mediateks.

- Information resources and platforms: Engineering educators teach the use of important information resources and platforms, such as internet sites, virtual libraries, video textbooks and online educational platforms.

- Integration of MediaTek: engineer-educators draw up exercises to ensure the integration of MediaTek into the educational process. Through these exercises, students learn how to use Mediatek and look for information.

- Ethical aspects of mediamadanism: engineer-educators explain to students the ethical aspects of mediamadanism, such as how much to avoid plagiarism, regulate information as the right source, and protect personal information.

- Media analytics: engineer-educators strive to educate students in media analytics. It gives students the basic principles of Information Analysis and mediasozing.

These are all elements that are part of the content of the development of mediamadanism in engineering educators. Through these contents, engineering educators prepare students to be not successful in a World targeted at media yoshina.

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